

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF CFRP BOLTED JOINTS USING BONDED INSERTS

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SUMMARY: A numerical and experimental investigation into the use of bonded metallic inserts to increase the strength of composite bolted joints is presented. Metallic inserts bonded to the surface of the hole of a composite laminate redistribute the radial stresses applied to the composite. The numerical models and the experiments performed in double-shear bolted joints show that there is premature yielding and fracture of the adhesive and no improvement on the joint strength. A new insert design is proposed for single-shear joints. Using tapered end inserts the maximum load sustained by single-shear joints is increased due to the creation of new load patches.

KEYWORDS: Mechanically fastened joints, bonded inserts.

INTRODUCTION

The use of mechanical fasteners to join composite structures is widespread throughout the aerospace industry. The tolerance to environmental effects, the ease of inspection and assembly, and the possibility of part replacement are the main advantages of this technique [(1)] However, even for optimized combinations of laminate lay-up, stacking sequence and joint geometry, low efficiencies occur due to the high stress concentrations and to the brittle nature of most fibre-reinforced composites [(2)]. A low efficiency leads to weight and cost penalties in composite structures. It is therefore important to develop new techniques to improve the efficiency of mechanically fastened joints.

The use of metallic inserts bonded to the hole of the laminate has been proposed as a technique to improve the efficiency of composite bolted joints [(3)]-[(6)]. Using adhesively bonded inserts the radial stresses due to the hole-bolt contact are transferred using the whole surface of the hole. Therefore, the bearing stress concentration factor [(7)] is reduced. However, both experimental [(4)] and numerical investigations [(3)] have shown that the adhesive fails before the full strength of the laminate is attained.

The objective of the current work is to develop new insert designs to improve the efficiency of single-shear and double-shear composite bolted joints. Numerical models of different insert configurations, using both straight and tapered ends, are developed to assess the most adequate geometry. The models are able to predict the stress redistribution obtained when bonded inserts are used, yielding in the adhesive. Using a previously proposed progressive damage model [(8)] the different damage mechanisms and failure modes occurring in the composite can also be predicted.

Based on the results of the numerical models, specimens representing single-shear and double-shear bolted joints are manufactured and tested to assess the gains obtained using metallic bonded inserts.

NUMERICAL MODELS

A finite element model representing a joint designed to fail by bearing is created using ABAQUS [(9)] software. Two models are created: double-shear and single-shear bolted joints in a $(0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ)_{2s}$ CFRP laminate loaded in tension.

1. *Simulation of the adhesive*: it has been shown [(10)] that the yielding of epoxy resins depends on both hydrostatic and deviatoric stress components. As a consequence, different yield stresses occur in uniaxial tension and compression. Previous analyses of adhesively bonded joints [(11)] have used Raghava's [(12)] pressure dependent yield criterion in epoxy polymers. Such a criterion is used in the current model and is expressed by:

$$2\sigma_Y^C\sigma_Y^T = (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2 + 2(\sigma_Y^C - \sigma_Y^T)(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3) \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are the principal stresses and σ_Y^C, σ_Y^T are the adhesive yield stresses in compression and tension respectively.

In order to predict adhesive failure, the post-yielding behavior of the material must be modeled: non-associated plasticity and work-hardening conditions are used and, since the structure under investigation is loaded monotonically, isotropic hardening is assumed. An epoxy adhesive whose properties were obtained in a previous work [(11)] is simulated.

The adhesive tensile stress-strain curve, required as a model input to define the adhesive yielding behavior, was obtained experimentally by Charalambides et al. [(14)]. Based on the experimental data [(14)], a number of points, in the form of stress-plastic strain, are implemented in ABAQUS [(9)]. These points are used in the interpolation of the yield stress at a given strain.

Based on previous investigations [(11)], it is assumed that the adhesive fails when the equivalent plastic strain reaches 0.0063. The equivalent plastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}$ is defined by:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl} = \int \frac{1}{\sigma_Y^T} \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^{pl} \quad (2)$$

2. *Double-shear joint*: a Texipreg HS 160 REM CFRP laminate is simulated. The 2mm-thick, $(0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ)_{2s}$ CFRP laminate was manufactured accordingly to the manufacturer's specifications. The ply properties were obtained following ASTM standards, and are shown in Tables 1 to 3.

Table 1 Ply elastic properties (GPa)

E_1	E_2	E_3	G_1	G_{13}	G_{23}
130	8.7	8.7	3.5	3.5	2.9

*transverse isotropy assumed

Table 2 Ply Poisson ratios

ν_{12}	ν_{23}^*	ν_{13}^*
0.33	0.52	0.33

*transverse isotropy assumed

Table 3 Ply strengths (MPa)

X^+	X^-	Y^+	Y^-	S^{xy}
2400.0	900.0	44.5	200.0	43.0

The geometry used follows the recommendations to promote a bearing failure in the composite. The geometry used in the models is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Composite specimen geometry

	d (mm)	t (mm)	w/ e	e/ t
No insert	6	2	6	3
Insert	10	2	6	3

w: width; d: hole diameter; e: end distance; t: specimen thickness

The presence of a three-dimensional state of stress in the vicinity of the loaded hole of the composite requires a three-dimensional model to capture stress components that can affect the onset and the propagation of the damage occurring in composite bolted joints [(1)]. Therefore, a three-dimensional finite element model using one element to model each ply of the laminate is used. The use of one three-dimensional element per ply thickness assures a reasonable representation of the through-thickness stresses occurring on the vicinity of the hole [(8)]. To simulate the contact between the bolt and the insert, linear eight-node isoparametric three-dimensional solid elements are used.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the radial stresses along the composite's hole, normalized by the bearing stress defined as:

$$S_b = \frac{P}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1 Redistribution of radial stresses

It can be seen that when bonded inserts are used the load is transferred using the whole surface of the hole, where compressive radial stresses occur for $\theta < 90^\circ$ and tensile radial stresses for $\theta > 90^\circ$. The lower

compressive stresses occurring in the bearing plane using steel inserts are compensated by higher tensile stresses for $\theta > 90^\circ$.

The predicted loads to cause yield (P^Y) and failure (P^U) in the adhesive are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Predicted adhesive yielding and failure loads (double-shear)

P^Y (N)	P^U (N)
2834.0	4232.0

The numerical models predict that the adhesive yields and fails before the laminate. This effect may eliminate the potential benefits of using bonded metallic inserts in double-shear joints.

3. *Single-shear joint*: three-dimensional models of CFRP single-lap joints are created using laminated brick solid elements. Taking into account that bolt-bending is more pronounced in a single-shear joint, the bolt is simulated as a flexible body. In order to reduce the size of the model the bolt is simulated with an internal hole. In order to correctly account for the bending of a solid bolt, an equivalent elastic modulus, E_{FE} , calculated from the equation $E_{Al}I_S = E_{FE}I_{FE}$ is used. E_{Al} is the Young's modulus of aluminium, I_S is the moment of inertia of the solid bolt, and I_{FE} is the moment of inertia of the bolt simulated in the numerical model. The mesh of the single-shear joint is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Mesh of single-shear joint without insert

Contact conditions are specified between the bolt and the two laminates, and, in order to avoid interpenetration of the two plates, between the surfaces of the laminates.

Considering the results obtained in the double-shear model, different insert geometries are simulated. Taking into account that in a single-shear joint the insert can be extended to the outer surface of a laminate, the insert geometries represented in Figure 3 are proposed.

Fig. 3 Insert geometries

The tapered inserts A) and B) are designed in order to provide a new load path for the load transfer (by shear stresses along the tapered end of the insert), therefore further reducing stress concentrations in the composite. Tapered inserts also have the advantage of avoiding the through-the-thickness expansion of the material subjected to the bolt bearing load. Insert C) is a straight insert similar to the ones used in double-shear joints.

Figure 4 shows the mesh of the single-shear bolted joints using inserts types A) and B).

Fig. 4 Mesh of single-shear joint with inserts types A) and B)

Table 6 shows the predicted yield and failure load of the adhesive for the 3 cases under investigation.

Table 6 Predicted adhesive yielding and failure loads (single-shear)

Insert type	P^Y (N)	P^U (N)
A)	667.3	1165.4
B)	660.4	1153.0
C)	507.9	914.3

The insert type A) provides the highest loads for both adhesive yielding and failure. Furthermore, the joint stiffness is maximised when using insert type A).

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

1. *Double-shear joint*: test specimens, corresponding to the geometry and material used in the numerical models, were manufactured. The aluminum insert thickness is 1.875mm and an epoxy adhesive (Vantico 420AB) is used. Following the manufacturer's recommendations, the adhesive thickness is 0.125mm. The geometry of the joints under investigation is shown in Table 4. The adhesive properties are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Adhesive properties

E (G P a)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile elongation (%)
1.9	32	4

The specimens were tested under displacement control, at a speed of 2mm/min, at ambient conditions (T=23°C, 50% humidity).

The load-cross head displacement relation obtained in the experiments is shown in Figure 5. Table 8 shows the maximum loads obtained in double-shear joints with and without inserts.

Fig. 5 Load-displacement relation for double-shear joints

Table 8 Maximum loads for double-shear specimens (average values)

	P ^{MAX} (N)
No in se	12734

rt	
Al insert	10914

As predicted by the numerical models, the use of bonded aluminium inserts does not improve the strength of a double-shear composite bolted joint. As shown in Figure 6, the adhesive fails in the region subjected to tensile stresses. After adhesive failure, the insert is unable to redistribute the radial stresses in the composite hole.

Fig. 6 Failed double-shear specimen

The stiffness of the joint is also reduced by the presence of a bonded insert. This effect can be related with the low elastic modulus of the adhesive and to premature yielding of the adhesive and of the aluminium insert.

The sequence of microscopic fracture mechanisms can be monitored, in real-time, from the rapid release of elastic strain energy they generate, detected at the surface of the material in the form of elastic waves (Acoustic Emission). For AE analysis, a two-channel AMSY-5 AE system developed by Vallen-System GmbH was used. AE events have been detected by two piezoelectric transducers. A resonant (150 kHz), Micro 80 from Physical Acoustics Corporation and a wide-band B1025, from DigitalWave Corporation, with a near flat frequency response from 50 kHz to 1.5 MHz. The transducers were mounted on the specimen using a tape. Silicone grease was used as coupling agent between the sensor and the composite surface. The preamplification of the AE signals was provided by two preamplifiers 1220A (PAC) with a gain selected to 40 dB and a high pass 100 kHz plug-in filter. The AE acquisition was triggered by threshold crossing. A threshold of 33.2 dB was used considering background noise. Transient signals were digitized at a sampling rate of 10 MHz in 1024 points data sets. Damage initiation can be determined by the increase of AE activity observed in the Cumulative AE hits vs. Time curves in Figures 7 and 10.

Fig. 7 AE activity observed during a double-shear test

Comparing the AE activity for a double-shear joint with insert (Figure 7-b)) and without insert (Figure 7-a)), a damage initiation delay is observed due to the presence of the insert. Without insert, AE is observed at 8000 N, whereas with insert AE activity increases at 11000 N just after adhesive failure.

For the specimen with the insert, AE starts after adhesive failure, indicating an increase of the bearing damage in the composite.

2. *Single-shear joint*: following the results of the numerical models, only aluminum inserts of type A) were manufactured. The load-cross head displacement relation obtained in the experiments is shown in Figure 8. Table 8 shows the maximum loads obtained in double-shear joints with and without inserts.

Fig. 8 Load-displacement relation for single-shear joints

Table 8 Failure loads for single-shear specimens (average values)

	P^{MAX} (N)
No insert	8088
Insert type A)	10660

The use of bonded aluminium inserts type A) increases by 24.1% the maximum load sustained by a single-shear composite bolted joint. The failure load, taken as the load at first load drop, corresponds to adhesive failure. No significant damage in the composite was found at that load. This is not the case for the specimen without insert: failure occurs due a significant amount of damage in the bolt bearing region of the laminate.

As shown in Figure 9, the adhesive initially fails along the interface between the top surface of the laminate and the tapered end of the insert.

Fig. 9 Failed single-shear specimen

The cumulative AE hits vs. Time curve is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10 AE activity observed during a single-shear test

Similarly to the double-shear tests, comparing the AE activity for single-shear with insert (Figure 10-b)) and without insert (Figure 10-a)) there is a damage initiation delay due to the bonded insert. When no insert is used, AE is observed at 7000 N. For the specimen with insert, significant AE activity starts at 12000 N after the complete failure of the adhesive. After the initial cracking of the adhesive, occurring at the tapered end at a load of 9000N, there is no significant AE due to the presence of alternative load patches. At 12000N the AE increases significantly, thus indicating damage in the composite laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of metallic bonded inserts to improve the efficiency of CFRP bolted joints is only effective for single-shear joints and using novel insert designs.

For double-shear joints, the adhesive interface between the CFRP laminate and the metallic insert fails due to the tensile stresses applied to the adhesive. After adhesive failure, the insert is unable to redistribute the stresses in the composite and the joint fails by bearing.

When using tapered end inserts, new load patches in the joint are promoted. Besides transferring the load using the whole shank of the hole, there is also load transferred by the shear stresses occurring at the interface between the tapered end of insert and the surface of the laminate. Under these circumstances, the maximum load sustained by the joint is increased by 24.1% when compared with that of a joint without insert.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge financial support of the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under the project POCTI/EME/43525/2000.

REFERENCES

- (1) Camanho P.P., Matthews F.L. “*Stress Analysis and Strength Prediction in FRP Joints: a Review*”. *Composites-Part A*, 28, pp. 529-547 (1997).
- (2) Hart-Smith L.J. “*Design and analysis of bolted and riveted joints in fibrous composite structures*”. *Douglas Paper 7739, McDonnell Douglas Corporation* (1986).
- (3) Camanho P.P, Matthews F.L. “*Bonded Metallic Inserts for Bolted Joints in Composite Laminates*”. *Journal of Materials: Design and Applications- Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part L*, 214, pp. 33-40 (2000).
- (4) Mirabella S, Galea S.L. “*An experimental study into the use of inserts to enhance the static performance of thin composite bolted lap joints*”. *11th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Gold Coast, Australia. 1997, pp. 148-57 (1997).
- (5) Nilsson S. “*Increasing the strength of graphite/epoxy bolted joints by introducing an adhesively bonded metallic insert*”. *Journal of Composite Materials*; 23, 643-50 (1989).
- (6) Rufin A.C. “*Fastener hole reinforcement in composites using cold expanded inserts*”. *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, 17, pp. 145-51(1995).
- (7) Crews J.H, Hong C.S, Raju I.S. “*Stress-Concentration Factors for Finite Orthotropic Laminates With a Pin-Loaded Hole*”. *NASA TP 1862, National Aeronautics and Space Administration*, (1981).
- (8) Camanho P.P, Matthews F.L. “*A Progressive Damage Model for Mechanically Fastened Joints in Composite Laminates*”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 33, pp.2248-80 (1999)
- (9) Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorensen. *ABAQUS 6.2 User's Manual*. Pawtucket, U.S.A. (1996).
- (10) Adams, R.D. “*Theoretical stress analysis of adhesively bonded joints. in Joining Reinforced Plastics*”, F. L. Matthews, ed., Elsevier, Barking (1987).
- (11) Charalambides, M.N., Kinloch, A.J. and Matthews, F.L. “*Adhesively-bonded repairs to fibre-composite materials- II: finite element characterization*”. *Composites-Part A*, 29, pp.1383-1396 (1998).
- (12) Raghava, R., Caddell, R.M. and Yeh, G.S. “*The macroscopic yield behavior of polymers*”. *Journal of Materials Science*, 8, pp.225-232 (1973).
- (13) Rice, J.R. “*Continuum mechanics and thermodynamics of plasticity in relation to microscale deformation mechanisms*”. in *Constitutive Equations in Plasticity*, A. S. Argon, ed., MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts (1975).
- (14) Charalambides, M.N., Hardouin, R., Kinloch, A.J. and Matthews, F.L. “*Adhesively-bonded repairs to fibre-composite materials- I: experimental studies*”. *Composites-Part A*, 29, pp. 1371-1381 (1998).